

Research

The Distribution and Availability of Inorganic Phosphorus Fractions along Altitudinal Gradient: A Case Study of Himalayan Kashmir, Pakistan

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Abstract

In vulnerable ecological regions, understanding factors which affect distribution of soil nutrients is very critical for management of fertilizers and protection of environment. Two vital aspects which describe terrestrial environment in relation to natural and anthropogenic processes are Land Use (LU) and Land Cover (LC). The cohesive term Land Use Land Cover (LULC) includes both categories of LU and LC and analysis of changes is of prime importance to understanding many social, economic, and environmental problems. In recent years, LULC change analysis has emerged as an important research question, because LULC change has been identified as a key factor which stands responsible for environmental modification worldwide. In Azad Jammu and Kashmir (AJ&K) deforestation and land-use/land-cover (LULC) changes have increased over the past decades especially in Muzaffarabad division after the massive earthquake of 2005, consequently the increased demand for agricultural products, building materials, land for construction etc. Anyhow P is one of the most important nutrients for the growth of plants and crops. But the effect of LULC is uncertain on Availability of P. The objective of this study will be to assess the impacts of LULC change on soil inorganic and organic P fractions of different availability (modified Hedley sequential fractionation) and on P stocks in soils under different land uses along an altitudinal of at least four (04) altitude categories in District Muzaffarabad. The outcome of this study is helpful in convincing the farmers adopt agroforestry practices and maintain soil cover in large scale in this highly vulnerable area of Azad Jammu and Kashmir. Results showed that the highest P observed was 0.1 M HCl (moderately available) that is associated with apatite and Ca-P compounds that could be the evidence of presence of the moderately labile P present in calcareous soils. The overall TP was found highest (900 mg Kg⁻¹) in 0 – 5 cm depth and minimum (200 mg Kg⁻¹) was recorded in 15 – 30 cm. The available P (resin P) was also found highest (60 mg Kg⁻¹) at depth of 5 cm while minimum (10 mg Kg⁻¹) was found in L1 at depth of 30 cm. From all results of the soils analyzed for P fractions it could be observed that altitude influenced the P fractions at different depths. The variations in P fractions are associated to the land use

type e.g., highest P values were always found in close canopy forests.

Keywords: Phosphorous, Inorganic Fractions, Gradient, Land Use, Land Cover, Peer Chinasi

1. Introduction

Phosphorus P plays an important role in the growth and production of plants as well as essential for microorganism, in soil it is found in two forms organic and inorganic P (Hou *et al.*, 2020). Inorganic P consists of primary and secondary minerals while organic P is made up of orthophosphate monoesters, nucleic acid, phosphates and acids (Luo *et al.*, 2020). Litter from plants and grasses increase the concentration of nutrients in soil, these are main sources of fertility increase in soil by decomposition and nutrient cycling processes (Luo *et al.*, 2021). It is understood that all forests are found on mountains, so elevation and spatial variability is the main factor in nutrient cycling (Johnson *et al.*, 2003). Availability of nutrients, such as phosphorous increase and acidity of soil also increase because of increase in elevation from sea level, as oceans exert various biogeochemical effects on formation of soil and nutrient cycling (Sidorova *et al.*, 2014). Anthropogenic activities affect land use and land cover so we can easily find the impact of human activities on soil by LULC changes (Cheng *et al.*, 2018 and Elledge and Thorten, 2017). LULC change affects soil quality), runoff and sedimentation rates (Cheng *et al.*, 2018), and biodiversity and ecosystem services (Zhang *et al.*, 2016). In this context of LULC change in Azad Jammu and Kashmir (AJ&K) and particularly in Muzaffarabad, after the devastating earthquake of 2005, there is a continued decline in forest cover due to increase demand for construction wood, land for home construction etc. degradation of soil is the main component of degradation of land (Yan *et al.*, 2013).

In 2010 the estimated total area of forest was four billion hectares which was 31% of total land of the world (FAO, 2010). Which is decreasing day by day due to deforestation, caused by forest fire, drought, human activity and change of land use etc. (FAO, 2010). However, change of land use from forests to crop land or into pastures affect the properties of soil. The impact of change of soil properties has several factors such as how the forests are cleared, the exposure of pesticides and insecticides, and climatic and morphological changes and pedagogical conditions as well. These factors cause soil erosion and affect the uptake of nutrients and affect the degradation of soil. Due to deforestation, there are number of changes to C, N, and other nutrients dynamics. (Wang and Liang, 2014). Due to land use changes soil aggregate stability and compaction also disturbed (Teferi *et al.*, 2016). Number of articles have discussed soil compaction and aggregate stability due to land use changes and focus on soil fauna and microbial biomass (Lu *et al.*, 2014).

One of the biggest problems is land degradation due to these worse conditions are expected (Millennium Ecosystem Assessment, 2005). The valuation of dry land response to changing stress is therefore of utmost importance to dry lands where these communities have been spreading over the last few decades as a result of secondary succession in abandoned fields and recurrently burned pine woodlands (Deiss *et al.*, 2018) and they are expected to cover larger areas in the future due to increased fire frequency and climate warming (Lou *et al.*, 2015). In many cases, the vegetation cover of Mediterranean shrub lands is discontinuous or fragmented due to different disturbance agents such as overgrazing, drought, and/or adverse conditions preventing a complete recovery of vegetation after fire (e.g., post-fire drought, high fire severity or recurrence) (Costa *et al.*, 2016; Almagro *et al.*, 2013). In the present context of climate change, increasing drought and fire risk will further reduce plant cover (Klí and Ondra, 2013).

Litter fall is the massive natural source for nutrient influx to forest ecosystem through nutrient recycling and decomposition (Schaap *et al.*, 2021). High decomposition of litter provides nutrients to plants while less decomposition develops organic matter of soil (Gatti *et al.*, 2021). Decomposition of litter consists of depolymerization, fragmentation and mineralization of organic matter, i.e., litter mass loss and nutrient release (Helfenstein *et al.*, 2020). These processes affect litter quality, i.e., contents of nitrogen (N), phosphorus (P), potassium (K), carbon (C), lignin, cellulose and hemicellulose, and the physicochemical environment (Alvarez and Noellemeyer, 2022; Bohara *et al.*, 2020). Thus, in the context of this background and due to a sharp shift in LULC change in the study area, our objectives were to provide insight into the soil total P distribution along the altitudinal gradient as well as soils under different LULC types. To test if the fate of inorganic P in the tree sapling-soil system differs between different LULC sites. To assess the influence of plant residues on the fate of organic P under different LULC sites.

2. Materials and Methods

The investigation zone lies in lesser Himalayan lower regions of Azad Jammu and Kashmir in District Muzaffarabad, AJ&K study was finished during 2019. The most smoking with a long time with normal temperature is 23 °C. The examined territory is situated at 73° 32' 51.9900" East longitude and 34° 23' 16.0044" North Latitude. The altitudinal scope

of study territory is from 900 m in Muzaffarabad city to 2900 m at Peer Chinasi. The region displays a sticky sub-tropical to calm environment with warm summers joined by a rainstorm season followed by genuinely chilly winters. January and February are the coldest months of the year with normal temperature is 8°C. The normal precipitation is around 1000 mm. Snowfall happens in January and February at higher heights.

2.1. Study sites and sampling

Five sites were chosen in the investigation region going in elevation from 900 to 2900 m disseminated in four height ranges. In first site, three woods patches were chosen going in height from 900 to 1400 m. These were (I) Closed shade woods (ii) Open backwoods (iii) Disturbed woodland. Three soil tests from the profundities of 0–5, 5–10, 10–15 and 15–30 cm was taken at each plot. Four samples were taken from the edge of each quadrat and one from the middle. Similarly testing was done in different destinations (for example 900–1400, 1400–1900, 1900–2400, 2400–2900 m or more). Three soil tests were taken from every profundity of 0–5, 5–15, and 15–30 cm at the close by farming area at each site. The longitude and scope of each site was estimated with the help of GPS. Soil tests taken from three focuses at each examining site were blended well indeed and a composite sample was arranged likewise.

Table 2.1. The details of eleven sampled locations along with coordinates

Sampling place	Coordinates		Altitude (m)	Vegetation cover
	N	E		
Mera tanolian	34° 21528	73° 29417	953	Arable land
Batlian	34° 21746	73° 30072	1200	Grassland
Khilan	34° 21782	73° 30381	1296	Close canopy forest
Botha	34° 21928	73° 30171	1301	Disturbed forest
Botha	34° 21950	73° 30385	1398	Open forest
Niaz pura	34° 21844	73° 31127	1508	Open forest
Niaz pura	34° 21876	73° 31428	1560	Arable land
Upper Batlian	34° 21361	73° 31544	1921	Grassland
Riyan	34° 22195	73° 32872	2093	Open forest
Banda di gali	34° 22098	73° 32007	2127	Close forest
Peer chinasi top	34° 22330	73° 32921	2870	Grassland

2.2. Complementary physicochemical analysis of soil

Total organic carbon (TOC) was controlled by utilizing altered Mebius strategy (Nelson and Sommers, 1982). Momentarily, 0.5 g soil was processed with 5 mL of 1.0 N $K_2Cr_2O_7$ and 10 mL of H_2SO_4 at 150 °C for 30 min, reviews were at that point titrated with normalized $FeSO_4$. Additionally, soil pH and EC were evaluated.

2.3. Phosphorus fractionation

Air dried, ground, passed through sieve with 2 mm mesh size was used for all analysis. Keeping in see the target to survey the dirt bound P liability, successive P fractionation conspires proposed by Hedley et al. (1982) with little changes as proposed by Condron *et al.* (1985) was picked. At each progression, 10 mL of extractant was added to 0.5 g soil in a 15 mL rotator tubes (1:20 proportion) and the cylinders were vertically shaken on end-over-end at 60 rpm for 16 h at 25°C. The anion trade layer strips were utilized in the principal extraction during fractionation before immersion with $NaHCO_3$ as depicted by Gatiboni *et al.* (2005). To guarantee the extraction effectiveness both natural phosphorous (OP) and complete phosphorous (TP) was estimated by the strategy for Olsen and Sommers (1982). The OP was assessed by start technique and will be determined by the distinction between the measure of P removed with 0.5 M H_2SO_4 from touched off (550°C, 4 h) and non-lighted soil tests, while TP was assessed by assimilation with H_2SO_4 and H_2O_2 within the sight of soaked $MgCl_2$ and both were therefore decided calorimetrically by the strategy for Murphy and Riley (1962).

Fig. 2.1. Hedley Fractionation Scheme

2.4. Statistical analysis

The measurable investigation was completed utilizing Statistica programming (11.2). The correlations among inspecting destinations and height at every assortment examining site was performed utilizing the non-parametric trial of Kruskal-Wallis (H). The H test permits testing the invalid speculation that the methods estimations of tests locales or seasons at every assortment examining site are something similar. The test was applied by Equation 2:

$$H = \frac{12}{n(n+1)} \sum_{s=1}^k \frac{R_s^2}{n_1} - 3(n+1)$$

Where,

R_s was the amount of the "positions" involved by each testing site or height, n₁ was the quantity of perceptions; n, was the amount of n₁'s; and k was the quantity of examining destinations or elevation angle.

3. Results and Discussions

3.1. Basic physicochemical characteristics of soil

The total organic carbon (TOC) values were varied drastically in all three depths at all locations. Figure 3.1 shows the spatial and altitudinal variation in TOC (%) values. The overall TOC ranged between 0.5 to 33 % at L1 (arable land) and L3 (Close canopy) respectively at 0 – 5 and 15 – 30 cm depths. In 0 – 5 and 5 – 15 cm highest TOC (4.5% and 3.25%) were found at L10 (close canopy forest) and on the other hand 33% was highest value at L3 (close canopy). The TOC was different at different altitudes but there was no pattern found along with increasing altitude at all sampling points. After 1900 m height there was a short a pattern found till 2400 m and at 2900 m the TOC values declined.

The electrical conductivity (EC) values were not varied in all three depths at all locations. Figure 3.2 shows no spatial

and altitudinal variation in EC ds m^{-1} values. The overall EC ranged between 1.1 to 2.8 ds m^{-1} at L7 (arable land) and L6 (Open Forest) respectively at 0 – 5 and 15 – 30 cm depths. In 0 – 5 and 5 – 15 cm highest EC (2.8 ds m^{-1} and 2.9 ds m^{-1}) were found at L6 (open forest) and on the other hand 2.9 ds m^{-1} was highest value at L4 (disturbed forest). There were slight variations in values of EC in all locations but slightly high at 1400 – 1900 m then became constant along with gradient.

The pH of soil samples varied between 6.8-7.9 along with gradient as well as depth. Figure 3.3 showed that the highest pH value was noticed at L3 (close canopy forest) and lowest was noticed in L9 (open forest) which was 7.9 and 6.8, respectively. Although there was slight change in pH along with altitude and depth as well.

Value of soil EC decline with increase in altitude as for both ammonium and nitrate. EC and ammonium contents are higher in crust soil than that of grassland. Ammonium and EC were greater in the crust soil than the grass soil, but nitrate concentration was the same under both plant covers. Using these measured gradient relationships, the increase in temperature and decrease in precipitation that is expected in this shrub steppe ecosystem over the next 100 years would eventually cause the pH to increase and the EC to decrease (Smith *et al.* 2002). The most important components of soil and sediments as well are total organic carbon (TOC) and total nitrogen (TN), these both are key factors of soil fertility. These both can be used to distinguish the source of organic matter whether it comes from marine sources or comes from terrestrial sources. These can also monitor soil quality, soil productivity, pollution indices and environmental depositional conditions (Avramidis *et al.* 2014; Alvarez and Noellemeyer, 2022).

Fig. 3.1. Variations in Total organic carbon (TOC) for all four altitudinal zones (900, 1400, 1900, 2400, 2900 m) and all 11 locations (n = 3). The figure from above to lower shows the three depths (0 – 5, 5 – 15 and 15 – 30 cm).

Fig. 3.2. Variations in electrical conductivity (EC) for all four altitudinal zones (900, 1400, 1900, 2400, 2900 m) and all 11 locations (n = 3). The figure from above to lower shows the three depths (0 – 5, 5 – 15 and 15 – 30 cm).

Fig. 3.3. Variations in pH for all four altitudinal zones (900, 1400, 1900, 2400, 2900 m) and all 11 locations (n = 3). The figure from above to lower shows the three depths (0 – 5, 5 – 15 and 15 – 30 cm).

3.2. Comparison of biological available phosphorus (Resin-P)

Labile inorganic P (Resin P) values showed variability along with altitude. Figure 3.4 shows that the higher concentration of labile P was at L10 (close canopy forest) which was 60.2 mgKg⁻¹ and lowest concentration was reported at L1 (arable land) which was 11.4 mgKg⁻¹. Values of labile P also varied along with depth. It was lower in depth (0-5 cm) in location L1 and higher in depth (15-30cm) which were 60.2 mgKg⁻¹ and 11.4 mgKg⁻¹ respectively. It was reported that higher concentration was in close canopy forest than in open forest and grassland followed by disturbed forest and arable land. Feudis *et al.* (2016) conducted a study to evaluate the effect of rhizosphere on availability of P. P is very important nutrient for the growth of plants and crops as well, although plants are not able to uptake this nutrient from soil because P bounded with other elements of soil and converted into no-labile P. their results showed that at higher altitude rhizosphere activity is enhanced and availability of P and other nutrients also enhanced. So, at higher altitude labile P (Resin P) fraction is higher as compared to lower altitude.

Fig. 3.4. Variations in labile (Resin P) for all four altitudinal zones (900, 1400, 1900, 2400, 2900 m) and all 11 locations (n = 3). The figure from above to lower shows the three depths (0 – 5, 5 – 15 and 15 – 30 cm)

3.3. Comparison of 0.5 molar sodium bicarbonate extractable P (0.5 M NaHCO₃-P)

Labile inorganic P and labile organic (NaHCO₃ P) also changed along with locations and showed high variability with altitude. Figure 3.5 clearly describes the highest values of NaHCO₃ P at high altitude 2150 m in L10 (close canopy forest) and lowest was reported at L1 (arable land) which were 62.5 mgKg⁻¹ and 10.2 mgKg⁻¹ respectively. Values of NaHCO₃ P follow the pattern L10 > L3 > L5 > L11 > L9 > L8 > L2 > L4 > L6 > L7 > L1 which indicates that highest concentration is in close canopy forest followed by open forest and lowest concentration is in arable land. The figure also showed that the highest concentration is reported in depth (15-30 cm).

Zaho *et al.* (2019) explained that if Ca contents were high in soil it captured high amount of PO₄ but less amount of OP. due to higher amount of Ca contents in soil higher amount of P can bound with Fe and Al. but when anaerobic conditions are formed bounded P instantly converted into labile p. due to anaerobic conditions P weakly absorbed on crystalline compounds and compound with low recalcitrant converted into instantly labile P.

Fig. 3.5. Variations in NaHCO₃P for all four altitudinal zones (900, 1400, 1900, 2400, 2900 m) and all 11 locations (n = 3). The figure from above to lower shows the three depths (0 – 5, 5 – 15 and 15 – 30 cm).

3.4. Comparison of 0.1 molar sodium hydroxide extractable P (0.1 M NaOH-P)

Concentration of moderately labile P (0.1 M NaOH P) was higher in L6 (open forest) followed by L10 (close canopy forest) and L11 (grass land) respectively. Figure 3.6 elaborates that along with gradient the highest concentration was 450 mg Kg⁻¹ in L6 and lowest concentration was 190 mg Kg⁻¹. While along with depth the highest concentration of moderately labile P was reported in depth (5-15 cm) and lowest was reported in (15-30 cm).

Condron *et al.* (2005) conducted a study to evaluate the effect of temperature on P concentration in soil. They stated that with an increase in temperature Labile P concentration also increased in soil. Due to high temperature concentration of Fe and Al decreased in soil so P bounded with these elements became free and become instantly labile P. in other words we can say concentration of Labile P increased in soil due to increase in temperature. Alvarez and Noellemeyer (2022) also conducted a study to evaluate the cycling of P in different topographical soils, they also evaluate how the availability of P can be increased in soil. They examined that HCl-P fraction of phosphorus was higher in soil that was 20% of total P. Available P also have a higher concentration in NV land use.

Fig. 3.6. Variations in 0.1 M NaOH for all four altitudinal zones (900, 1400, 1900, 2400, 2900 m) and all 11 locations (n = 3). The figure from above to lower shows the three depths (0 – 5, 5 – 15 and 15 – 30 cm).

3.5. Comparison of Moderately available P (1M HCl-P)

From the figure 3.7 a huge variation can be noted in all depths as well as different location from 900 m to 2900 m altitude. In all three soil depths moderately available P (HCl 0.1 M) was minimum (45 to 75 mg Kg⁻¹) in arable land and the possible reason for less P (HCl 0.1 M) is development of soil and disturbing soil for agriculture, on the other hand when soil sample were collected the soil was under cultivation of maize that was at its maturity phase so It can be assumed that this P fraction was also up taken by crop plants. Highest P (HCl 0.1 M) was found in interval from 1900 m to 2400 m altitude while comparing the P fractions in depths a slight incline can be observed from L8 (grass land) to L10 (Close Forest – pine trees), the highest P values were in 0 – 5 cm depth (310 to 320 mg Kg⁻¹). The overall high P (moderately available P) could be an evidence of the presence of oxides and Ca-P compounds because all these three sites (grassland, open forest, and close forest) are the least disturbed areas of the selected site. A slight decline at L11 (grassland) could be associated with the human activities or human disturbing factor as the location was the top of the mountain and is known as a picnic spot and there is always an anthropic factor present at that location.

Moderately available P (HCl 0.1 M) is the fraction of P that is associated with apatite and other partially soluble Ca-P compounds or negatively charged oxides that were extracted as shown by Gatiboni et al. (2007). Zaho *et al.* (2019) explained that if Ca contents were high in soil it captured high amount of PO₄ but less amount of OP. due to higher amount of Ca contents in soil higher amount of P can bound with Fe and Al but when anaerobic conditions are formed P bounded appetite and other sparingly soluble Ca-P or negatively charged oxide surfaces instantly converted into labile P. Due to anaerobic conditions P weakly absorbed on crystalline compounds and compound with low recalcitrant converted into instantly labile P.

Fig. 3.7. Variations in 1 M HCl-P for all four altitudinal zones (900, 1400, 1900, 2400, 2900 m) and all 11 locations (n = 3). The figure from above to lower shows the three depths (0 – 5, 5 – 15 and 15 – 30 cm).

3.6. Comparison of 0.5 molar sodium hydroxide extractable P (0.5 M NaOH-P)

From the figure 3.8 a huge variation can be noted in all depths as well as different location from 900 m to 2900 m altitude. In all three soil depths non-labile P (NaOH 0.5 M) was minimum (40 to 80 mg Kg⁻¹) in disturbed forest and grassland. Highest P (HCl 0.1 M) was found in interval from 1900 m to 2400 m altitude while comparing the P fractions in depths a slight incline can be observed from location 3 (close canopy forest) to location 5 (open Forest), the highest P values were in 0 – 5 cm depth (210 to 270 mg Kg⁻¹). The overall high P (non-labile P) could be evidence of the presence of iron, aluminum, clay minerals, fulvic and humic acids. A decline at location 11 (grassland) could be associated with human activities or human disturbing factors as the location was the top of the mountain and is known as a picnic spot and there is always an anthropic factor present at that location.

Recalcitrant P (NaOH 0.5 M) is the non-labile fraction of P that is associated with iron, aluminum, and clay minerals in inorganic P form, and in form organic P form, it is associated with fulvic, and humic acid extracted as shown by (Gatiboni *et al.*, 2007; Alvarez and Noellemeyer, 2022). Rodrigues *et al.* (2016) arranged a study to know the legacy of P in agriculture land. They reported that with no tillage system the legacy of P and other fractions of P increased in surface layer. They further explained that 70-85% of applied P in the form of fertilizers bounded with Ca, Al, Fe or other clay minerals etc. and converted into moderately labile-P or non-labile P.

Fig. 3.8. Variations in 0.5 M NaOH-P for all four altitudinal zones (900, 1400, 1900, 2400, 2900 m) and all 11 locations (n = 3). The figure from above to lower shows the three depths (0 – 5, 5 – 15 and 15 – 30 cm).

3.7. Comparison of total phosphorous TP

Total P (TP) also showed variation in all locations along with gradient and as well as in three collection depths. The highest TP values were calculated at location 3 (close canopy forest) at all depths ranging from 800 mg Kg⁻¹ (15 – 30 cm) to 967 mg Kg⁻¹ (0 – 5 cm). Minimum TP were found at location 7 (220 mg Kg⁻¹) at depth 15 – 30 cm and 257 mg Kg⁻¹ at depth 0 – 5 cm. The overall TP was varied along with different altitudes and the overall deviation in TP could be associated to the land used types. The least disturbed areas having high values of TP and on other hand, disturbed and open areas show less P as compared to close canopy forest. The low values of grassland (2900 m) could be associated with anthropic activities.

Feudis *et al.* (2016) conducted a study to evaluate the effect of rhizosphere on availability of P. P is very important nutrient for the growth of plants and crops as well, although plants are not able to uptake this nutrient from soil because P bounded with other elements of soil and converted into no-labile P. their results showed that at higher altitude rhizosphere activity is enhanced and availability of P and other nutrients also enhanced. So, at higher altitude labile P (Resin P) fraction is higher as compared to lower altitude.

Fig. 3.9. Variations in total P (TP) for all four altitudinal zones (900, 1400, 1900, 2400, 2900 m) and all 11 locations (n = 3). The figure from above to lower shows the three depths (0 – 5, 5 – 15 and 15 – 30 cm)

Conclusion

This study investigated the P distribution along with increasing altitude at Himalayan foot hill peer chinasi (900 to 2900 m). The different P fractions were measured and there were huge differences among all fractions of P. The highest P observed was 0.1 M HCl (moderately available) that is associated with apatite and Ca-P compounds that could be the evidence of presence of the moderately labile P present in calcareous soils. The overall TP was found highest (900 mg Kg⁻¹) in 0 – 5 cm depth and minimum (200 mg Kg⁻¹) was recorded in 15 – 30 cm. The available P (resin P) was also found highest (60 mg Kg⁻¹) at depth of 5 cm while minimum (10 mg Kg⁻¹) was found in L1 at depth of 30 cm. From all results of the soils analyzed for P fractions it could be observed that altitude influenced the P fractions at different depths. The variations in P fractions are associated with the land use type e.g. highest P values were always found in close canopy forests.

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